

SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING PROGRAMS IN PROMOTING POSITIVE CLASSROOM CLIMATE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN LAMBAYONG III

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ABSTRACT

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) programs play a crucial role in fostering a positive classroom climate and enhancing students' emotional well-being. This phenomenological study explored teachers' perspectives on the impact of SEL programs in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2024-2025. A total of 10 teachers participated in semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, with data analyzed using thematic analysis. Findings reveal that SEL programs contribute to students' emotional awareness, improved peer and teacher relationships, and positive academic and behavioral outcomes. Students reported enhanced self-regulation, empathy, and stress management, leading to reduced anxiety and increased classroom engagement. SEL initiatives also strengthened peer interactions and student-teacher bonds, fostering a sense of belonging and reducing instances of bullying. Additionally, SEL programs promoted leadership and decision-making skills, helping students take responsibility for their actions and resolve conflicts effectively. Further analysis highlights students' recommendations for sustaining a positive classroom climate through SEL. They emphasized the importance of teacher guidance and support, open communication, and structured SEL activities such as team-building exercises and peer mediation programs. The study concludes that continuous implementation of SEL programs, along with teacher mentorship, is vital in creating an emotionally supportive and inclusive learning environment. The study recommends integrating SEL into the national curriculum, institutionalizing teacher training, and incorporating SEL activities into daily instruction.

Future research should explore the long-term impact of SEL on student performance and adaptability across diverse educational contexts.

Keywords: *social-emotional, learning program, positive classroom climate*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the importance of social-emotional learning (SEL) programs in educational settings worldwide. Social-emotional learning refers to the process through which individuals acquire and apply the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary to understand and manage emotions, set and achieve positive goals, feel and show empathy for others, establish and maintain positive relationships, and make responsible decisions (CASEL, 2020). Research has consistently demonstrated the positive impact of SEL programs on various outcomes, including academic achievement, social behavior, emotional well-being, and overall school climate (Durlak et al., 2011; Taylor et al., 2017).

Despite the increasing emphasis on SEL programs in international educational discourse, there remains a dearth of research specifically examining their role and effectiveness in the Philippine context. The Philippines, like many other countries, faces diverse challenges in its educational system, including issues related to student behavior, mental health, and school climate (Dumayaca & Velasco, 2019). Given the unique cultural, social, and economic context of the Philippines, it is essential to explore the implementation and impact of SEL programs within this context to inform policy and practice as this affects the satisfaction of teachers which sometimes caused them to leave their work and look for greener pasture overseas (Magonsik, & Ngag, 2025).

Furthermore, while existing research provides valuable insights into the general effectiveness of SEL programs, there is a need for more in-depth qualitative research to understand the lived experiences and perceptions of stakeholders. Particularly teachers, regarding the role of SEL in promoting a positive climate. Phenomenological analysis offers a valuable approach to explore individuals' subjective experiences and meanings attributed to specific phenomena, providing rich and nuanced insights into their perspectives (Moustakas, 1994).

Despite the burgeoning interest in social-emotional learning programs globally, there is limited empirical research specifically examining their implementation and impact in the Philippine educational context. Existing studies predominantly focus on quantitative evaluations of SEL programs' outcomes, with less attention given to qualitative exploration of stakeholders' perspectives. Furthermore, while quantitative research provides valuable data on the overall effectiveness of SEL programs, it may overlook the nuanced experiences and perceptions of individuals involved. Qualitative research methodologies, such as phenomenological analysis, offer an opportunity to delve deeper

into the subjective experiences of stakeholders, thereby providing a more holistic understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

Therefore, this study aims to address these research gaps by conducting a phenomenological analysis to explore teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III. By elucidating students' lived experiences and teachers' perceptions, this study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on SEL implementation and inform the development of contextually relevant and effective SEL interventions in the Philippines.

Research Question

This study aims to explore teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat.

Specifically, this delves with the following questions:

1. How do students perceive the impact of social-emotional learning programs on their emotional well-being and relationships with peers and teachers in Lambayong III?
2. What specific social and emotional skills do students report gaining from their participation in SEL programs?
3. How do students describe the influence of SEL programs on their attitudes towards learning, engagement in classroom activities, and overall classroom atmosphere in Lambayong III?
4. How do students suggest overcoming the challenges they encountered to further enhance the promotion of a positive classroom climate?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, a qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, will be employed to explore the teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024-2025.

Phenomenological research is a method that aims to delve into individuals' lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how they interpret these experiences. It operates under the assumption that individuals employ a universal structure or essence to derive meaning from their encounters (Dolutan, & Ngag, 2024). This research involves the interpretation of participants' emotions, perceptions, and beliefs to shed light on the fundamental essence of the phenomenon under investigation. An essential aspect of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's obligation to set aside any preconceived assumptions about the experience or phenomenon (Ho & Limpaecher, 2022).

Respondent of the Study

Table 1 displays the participants' qualifications, as determined by the criteria established by the researcher before selecting eligible informants for the study. Hence, the study involved a total of 10 teachers in Lambayong District III, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria:

Table 1. Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
<i>Participants: 10 Teachers</i>
Teaching Experience – Participants must be currently employed as teachers in Lambayong III and have at least three years of teaching experience to ensure they have sufficient exposure to classroom dynamics and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) programs.
Implementation of SEL Programs – Teachers must have actively participated in or implemented SEL programs within their classrooms, either as part of formal school initiatives or personal teaching strategies.
Willingness to Participate – Participants must provide informed consent and be willing to share their experiences, insights, and challenges related to SEL and its impact on classroom climate.
Diversity of Teaching Contexts – To ensure varied perspectives, participants should represent different grade levels and subject areas , reflecting diverse classroom settings where SEL strategies are applied.

Sampling Technique

During the conduct of this study, a Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the teachers in Lambayong District III, Sultan Kudarat division during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, alternately referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, constitutes a variant of non-probability sampling. Within this approach, researchers exercise their own judgment and discretionary acumen in the selection of individuals from the population to partake in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021).

Research Instruments

The researcher in this qualitative study will use a semi-structured interview as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs).

Its purpose is to facilitate an in-depth exploration of the teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the initial phase, researcher will diligently seek formal authorization from both the Superintendent of DepEd-Sultan Kudarat and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). This authorization is essential to obtain the necessary permissions for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

Following this, a secondary authorization letter will be sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire will be developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and then administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher will employ a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher will proceed with conducting interviews and facilitating Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), all of which will be conducted through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews and FGDs will be systematically organized, subjected to comprehensive analysis, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach is expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interviews and FGDs were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned their transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent phenomenological analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data:

Step 1: Audio Recording of Interviews

The first step in the transcription process involved audio recording interviews with the participants. For this study, researchers conducted in-depth interviews with teachers to explore their perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025. These interviews were recorded with explicit consent from the participants.

Step 2: Verbatim Transcription

Verbatim transcription was crucial as it captured participants' responses exactly as spoken, including pauses, hesitations, and emotional expressions. The researcher meticulously transcribed the audio recordings, ensuring the preservation of the precise language, grammatical structures, and speech patterns of the young learners interviewed.

Step 3: Researcher Verification

After transcription, the researcher verified the accuracy of transcripts by carefully reviewing them for any discrepancies or omissions. This step ensured that the written text faithfully represented the original audio recordings and maintained the integrity of the data collected.

Step 4: Participant Validation

Following transcription, the researcher shared the transcripts with participants for their review and feedback. Participants had the opportunity to validate the accuracy of their recorded responses, providing insights or clarifications where necessary. This process ensured that participants' perspectives were accurately represented in the study.

Step 5: Anonymization

To protect participants' confidentiality, the researcher anonymized transcripts by replacing any identifying information, such as names or specific locations, with pseudonyms or generic descriptors. This precautionary measure safeguarded the privacy of young learners involved in the study.

Data Analysis

In the context of the study on teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025, a thematic analysis approach was used to examine the collected data.

This methodology, as articulated by Flick (2014), and cited by Ngag (2023), this involved systematically categorizing textual components such as statements, phrases,

and words into organized groupings or categories. These categories were either derived from established frameworks or custom-developed to align with the study's specific objectives.

To execute this analytical process, a series of essential steps were diligently followed:

Initially, all data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from FGDs, and relevant documents, were meticulously organized and prepared for analysis. This phase ensured the systematic arrangement and accessibility of the data.

Subsequently, the researchers deeply engaged with the data by conducting a thorough review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the content and context embedded within the collected information.

The third step involved initiating a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data, capturing essential concepts, ideas, or themes related to the paperwork overload for teacher well-being.

Following coding, the identified codes were grouped into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step aimed to establish an initial structure for organizing the data and exploring teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025.

Next, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of review and refinement. The researcher ensured the consistency and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments as they interpreted the data in the context of teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotes or segments extracted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and associated with the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes, enhancing the credibility and depth of the analysis.

Finally, the thematic analysis extended beyond surface-level identification. Researchers interpreted the meaning and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, connections, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate.

Scope and Delimitation

The study was conducted in the Lambayong III District, a region characterized by its diverse teacher population and varied educational settings. The primary participants were teachers from selected schools within Lambayong III who have been actively involved in Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) programs. Additionally, school administrators and program coordinators may be included to provide a comprehensive view of the implementation and impact of SEL programs.

The study focused on SEL programs that have been implemented over the past three academic years (2021-2024) to capture both recent and ongoing experiences and outcomes.

The study excluded schools and participants that have not implemented any form of SEL programs. This exclusion is to maintain a focused examination on the effects of SEL initiatives specifically. Due to the qualitative nature of the study, the sample size was limited to a manageable number of participants who can provide rich, detailed insights into their experiences. This limitation is necessary to conduct in-depth interviews and analysis (Cerdana, & Ngag, 2024). The study focused on specific aspects of classroom climate influenced by SEL programs, such as student-teacher relationships, peer interactions, emotional safety, and overall classroom atmosphere. It did not over academic achievement or other unrelated aspects of classroom dynamics.

Generally, the findings were specific to the Lambayong III District and may not be generalizable to other regions with different cultural, socio-economic, or educational contexts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the importance of social-emotional learning (SEL) programs in educational settings worldwide. In this study, a qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to explore the teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024-2025. The study involved a total of 10 teachers in Lambayong District III, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. A semi-structured interview was used for interview and FGD. Thematic analysis was then utilized for the analysis of the data.

Thematic analysis of student perceptions reveals three key benefits of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) programs: enhanced emotional awareness, improved peer and teacher relationships, and positive behavioral and academic outcomes. Students reported that SEL programs help them recognize and regulate their emotions, fostering empathy and self-growth. Additionally, SEL initiatives strengthen student-teacher bonds and peer interactions, creating a sense of belonging and trust within the classroom. Students also noted reduced stress and anxiety levels, leading to improved academic

focus and better conflict resolution skills. Overall, these findings highlight the significant role of SEL programs in supporting students' emotional well-being, fostering positive relationships, and enhancing their academic and personal development.

Further, findings reveal that Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) programs significantly enhance students' social and emotional skills. First, SEL fosters improved socialization and teamwork, as students develop better peer interactions, actively participate in group activities, and collaborate effectively, leading to reduced bullying. Second, SEL strengthens emotional awareness and self-regulation, equipping students with skills to identify and manage their emotions, express themselves clearly, and utilize stress-management techniques. Lastly, SEL enhances leadership and decision-making skills, encouraging students to take responsibility, resolve conflicts, and make informed choices, with some even applying these skills to their relationships at home.

Furthermore, findings indicate that Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) programs positively influence students' attitudes toward learning and classroom engagement. First, SEL fosters increased participation and confidence, as students become more willing to share ideas and engage actively in classroom discussions. Second, SEL cultivates a stronger sense of belonging and peer support, creating a more inclusive and collaborative learning environment with reduced competition and bullying. Lastly, SEL enhances students' motivation and focus on learning by equipping them with resilience and stress-management skills, allowing them to handle academic challenges more effectively.

Finally, the results highlight students' suggestions for overcoming challenges in promoting a positive classroom climate through three key themes. First, teacher guidance and support play a crucial role, with students emphasizing the importance of teachers as role models who provide encouragement, structured activities, and emotional guidance. Second, enhanced communication and feedback are essential, as students recommend open communication, regular check-ins for concerns, and peer mediation programs to resolve conflicts before they escalate. Lastly, students advocate for structured activities and continuous SEL implementation, suggesting team-building exercises, clear classroom rules, and ongoing SEL programs to foster a more supportive and engaging learning environment.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made in light of this study's findings:

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) programs significantly contribute to students' emotional well-being by enhancing their ability to recognize, regulate, and express emotions effectively. Through SEL, students develop self-awareness, empathy, and stress-management skills, which support their emotional resilience and overall personal growth

SEL programs foster positive relationships between students and their peers, as well as with teachers, by promoting teamwork, collaboration, and inclusivity.

Strengthened peer and teacher relationships create a supportive learning environment where students feel a sense of belonging, reducing instances of bullying and fostering trust within the classroom.

SEL positively influences students' academic engagement and behavior by increasing their confidence, motivation, and ability to handle academic challenges. Through improved emotional regulation and decision-making skills, students demonstrate better focus, reduced anxiety, and enhanced participation in class discussions and activities

To sustain the benefits of SEL programs, continuous implementation and teacher support are essential. Students suggest structured team-building activities, clear classroom rules, regular check-ins, and peer mediation programs to strengthen the positive impacts of SEL. Teachers' role as mentors and role models remains crucial in fostering a nurturing and emotionally supportive classroom climate.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

1. DepEd may integrate Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into the national curriculum by developing structured SEL modules and training programs for teachers. These modules should focus on emotional awareness, peer collaboration, and leadership skills to support students' holistic development.
2. District Supervisors & School Administrators may institutionalize SEL initiatives by implementing regular teacher training on social-emotional learning strategies, fostering a supportive classroom environment, and establishing SEL-based student support programs, such as mentorship and peer mediation groups.
3. Educators may actively incorporate SEL activities into daily lessons by modeling positive behavior, conducting regular check-ins with students, and facilitating structured activities like team-building exercises, mindfulness practices, and conflict-resolution workshops to enhance emotional regulation and student engagement.
4. Future Researchers may explore the long-term impact of SEL programs on students' academic performance and emotional resilience. Additionally, research should investigate how SEL can be tailored for diverse cultural and socio-economic backgrounds to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness across various educational settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for conducting the study on teachers' perspectives on the role of social-emotional learning programs in promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025, all proposed plans and recommendations were formally presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc. to

ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols. Within the context of this research, which focused on exploring the paperwork overload for teacher well-being, it was crucial to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations.

Prior to commencing this study, the following ethical principles were meticulously observed:

Informed Consent:

Explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all parents or guardians of participating students. They were fully informed about the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Participation was voluntary, and participants had the autonomy to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality:

To protect the identities and responses of participants, stringent measures were implemented to maintain anonymity and confidentiality. Pseudonyms or codes were used instead of actual names, and all collected data were securely stored with limited access restricted to the research team.

Avoiding Harm:

Sensitive topics related to socio-emotional well-being and social media exposure were handled with careful consideration for potential emotional and psychological impacts on participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and support services were readily accessible as needed.

Researcher-Participant Relationship:

The researcher maintained a professional and respectful relationship with all participants, ensuring their dignity and well-being throughout the research process. Actions that could exploit or harm participants were strictly avoided.

Data Protection:

Stringent adherence to data protection regulations was upheld to safeguard all personal information collected during the study. Secure storage and transmission protocols were implemented to prevent unauthorized access.

Voluntary Participation:

Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was voluntary and free from coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias:

The researcher remained vigilant against biases that could influence data collection and analysis, promoting objectivity and transparency in reporting findings.

Institutional Approval:

Ethical clearance was sought from relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees prior to initiating the study.

Honesty and Integrity:

Research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, without manipulation or distortion, to uphold the integrity of the study.

Beneficence:

Potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were carefully considered, aiming to contribute positively to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity:

The researcher demonstrated cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, avoiding the imposition of external values on participants (Ronquillo, & Ngag, 2024).

Inclusion and Diversity:

The study prioritized inclusivity and diversity in participant selection, aiming to encompass a broad range of teachers' perspectives on promoting a positive classroom climate in Lambayong III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025.

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